

Solvent Effect on the Kinetics of Anation of Hydroxopentaquochromium(III) Ion by DL-Valine

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Spectrophotometric investigation of the titled reaction has been done at different temperatures (40–50°) and a rate law has been established in the pH range 4.5–5.2.

The values of the ion-pair equilibrium constant between substrate complex and zwitterionic valine (K_E) and the interchange rate constant from outer-sphere complex to inner-sphere product (k_a) have been discussed. Nitrate ion have been assumed to labilise the Cr–OH₂ bond through its specific attack on the coordinated water molecule. Effect of pH on rate has also been observed. Activation parameters have been calculated and compared with the data shown for isotopic water exchange process and other anation reactions of the same complex. An associative interchange (I_a) mechanism involving ion-pair formation has been suggested.

FOR anation of octahedral Cr^{III}-aquo-complexes by amino acid ligands, a well-known associative interchange (I_a) mechanism has been proposed^{1–5}. It has been suggested that amino acid (usually having N, O donor sites) ligands anate Cr(H₂O)₅(OH)²⁺ through associative path with the formation of ion-pair between the substrate complex ion and zwitterionic amino acid prior to the rate-determining step. Effect of dielectric constant of the reaction medium on anation rate constant (k_a) and ion-pair equilibrium constant (K_E) have recently been proved useful for diagnosis of the reaction mechanism^{6,7}. In this article we have tried to elucidate the probable mechanism of the reaction between Cr(H₂O)₅(OH)²⁺ and DL-valine by correlating the rate constant data with different solvent parameters (dielectric constant, Grunwald-Wienstein coefficient etc.).

Experimental

The reactant complex-I Cr(H₂O)₅(OH)²⁺ (log $\epsilon = 1.45$ at $\lambda_{\max} = 430$ and log $\epsilon = 1.25$ at $\lambda_{\max} = 590$ nm) was prepared^{10,11} *in situ* from [Cr(H₂O)₆](ClO₄)₃ by carefully adjusting pH(=5) of the solution of Cr(H₂O)₆³⁺.

Some Cr^{III}-aquo(amino acid) complex in solid state were isolated^{1–3}. However, the Cr^{III}-valine complex could not be isolated in solid state due to the hygroscopic nature of the product. Following technique was adopted to determine the composition of the reaction product. Complex-I and ligand valine were mixed in three different molar ratio (1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3) and heated at 50° for 48 h at a constant pH of 5. It was found that 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 mixtures gave identical spectra (log $\epsilon = 1.68$ at 540 nm and log $\epsilon = 1.58$ at 410 nm). A 1 : 2 metal-ligand composition of the maroon coloured reaction product was confirmed by Jobs' method of continuous variation, and that no retention of maroon colour was observed when the reaction

product was allowed to pass through both cation and anion exchanger resin which concludes 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio in the reaction product.

The course of the reaction was followed spectrophotometrically using a Hilger-UVISPEK spectrophotometer at 540 nm (marked difference existed between absorbance of complex-I and reaction product). Values of pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) were obtained by plotting log $(A_\infty - A_0)/(A_\infty - A_t)$ against time (where A_0 , A_t and A_∞ are the absorbances of the reaction mixtures at the start, at time t and after completion of the reaction respectively). All the kinetic experiments were repeated twice and the mean value of k_{obs} was taken.

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying [Complex-I] on rate: At different [Complex-I] (i.e. 0.002, 0.0025 and 0.003 mol dm⁻³) and at fixed [valH] (0.03 mol dm⁻³) and pH 5 and ionic strength (0.05 mol dm⁻³), the values of k_{obs} were 3.40, 3.44 and 3.51 × 10⁴ s⁻¹ respectively at 50° which shows that the rate of reaction is first order in [Complex-I].

Effect of varying pH on rate: In the studied pH range (4.5–5.2) ligand–DL-valine exists as zwitterion in the solution¹². First acid dissociation constant, i.e. pK_a value of Cr(H₂O)₆³⁺ is 3.8 at 25¹¹. So proton ambiguity (case arises if the pK_a values of complex-I and protonated ligand are comparable) is absent in the system. At fixed [Complex-I] (0.0025 mol dm⁻³), [valH] (0.03 mol dm⁻³) and ionic strength (0.05 mol dm⁻³) values of k_{obs} are 2.21, 2.89, 3.44 and 3.92 × 10⁴ s⁻¹ at pH 4.5, 4.8, 5.0 and 5.2 respectively. The increase in k_{obs} value with the increase of pH can be expressed by the equation,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2 K'_a [H^+]^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where k_1 is observed rate constant when the reacting complex is Cr(H₂O)₆³⁺ species, k_2 the observed

TABLE 1—VALUES OF k_{obs} AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN VARIOUS AQUO-ORGANIC MIXTURES
 ([Complex-I] = 0.0025 mol dm⁻³, pH = 5.0 and ionic strength = 0.05 mol dm⁻³)

[valH] mol dm ⁻³	30% (w/w) $k_{obs} \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹								
	Isopropanol - Water			Ethanol - Water			Methanol - Water		
	40°	45°	50°	40°	45°	50°	40°	45°	50°
0.0125	1.11	1.35	1.85	0.91	1.19	1.69	0.81	1.23	1.59
0.020	1.52	2.00	2.77	1.29	1.78	2.56	1.26	1.54	2.34
0.025	1.82	2.41	3.23	1.51	2.10	2.94	1.45	1.78	2.76
0.030	2.04	2.85	3.77	1.75	2.35	3.44	1.63	2.04	3.17
0.040	2.50	3.31	4.65	2.18	2.80	4.16	1.96	2.44	3.84
0.050	2.78	3.70	5.26	2.44	3.12	4.76	2.22	2.85	4.44

rate constant when the species is $Cr(H_2O)_5(OH)^{2+}$ and K'_a the proton dissociation constant of the system. Hence the increase in pH increases the amount of reactive hydroxo aqua species which increases the reaction rate. It is worthwhile to note that in the studied pH range 4.5–5.2, the plots of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ gave straight line. However departure from linearity was observed at higher pH range due to the change in reacting species.

Effect of varying [valH] on rate: The reaction was studied at three different temperatures (40, 45 and 50°) and the values of k_{obs} are given in Table 1, which shows that the increase in [valH] increases the reaction rate and at high ligand concentration limiting rate is reached (Fig. 1) indicating the completion of ion-pair formation^{1,5}.

Fig. 1. Plots of k_{obs} vs [valH] at different temperatures: (A) 50°, (B) 45° and (C) 40°; [Complex-I] = 0.0025 mol dm⁻³, pH = 5.0 and ionic strength = 0.05 mol dm⁻³.

A reaction scheme commensurating the above fact is proposed as follows.

The ring closure step (A→B) and the final step (B→C) are fast due to entry of one valine molecule in the inner coordination sphere which labilises the remaining water molecule by increasing the electron density on the metal ion. However, $[Cr(val)_3]^-$ is not formed as reaction product because stereochemically it is less stable than $[Cr(H_2O)(OH)(val)_2]$.

Considering the ion-pair equilibrium and rate-determining step, a rate expression is derived which can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{d[Cr(H_2O)(OH)(val)_2]}{dt} \\
 &= \frac{k_a K_E [Cr(H_2O)_5(OH)^{2+}]_T [valH]}{1 + K_E [valH]} \\
 &= k_{obs} [Cr(OH)(H_2O)_5^{2+}]_T \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where, } k_{obs} = \frac{k_a K_E [valH]}{1 + K_E [valH]} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{or } 1/k_{obs} = 1/k_a + 1/k_a K_E [valH] \quad (4)$$

It is seen from equation (4) that the plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[valH]$ at a constant pH should be linear with an intercept $1/k_a$ and slope $1/k_a K_E$ (Fig. 2). The values of k_a thus obtained are given in Table 2.

Fig. 2. Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[valH]$ at different temperatures: (A) 50°, (B) 45° and (C) 40°.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF k_a AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN DIFFERENT AQUO-ORGANIC MIXTURES

Temp.	80% (w/w) $k_a \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$		
	Isopropanol - Water	Ethanol - Water	Methanol - Water
40	6.45	5.01	4.17
45	9.12	7.41	6.45
50	14.45	12.80	10.47

K_E values lie in the range $10.2-22.3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ but at a given temperature the value increases with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Plots of $[\text{NO}_3^-]$ vs k_{obs} at different temperatures: (A) 50, (B) 45 and (C) 40°; 80% (w/w) ethanol-water mixture, $[\text{Complex-I}] = 0.0025 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{valH}] = 0.03 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 5.0$.

Catalysing effect of NO_3^- on rate: It was shown⁵ that nitrate ion having the tendency of expulsion of coordinated halide ion from metal centre can catalyse the rate of substitution reaction. At 50° it has been observed that the rate of anation reaction is increased with the increase in NO_3^- concentration at fixed $[\text{Complex-I}]$ ($0.0025 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), $[\text{valH}]$ (0.03 mol dm^{-3}) and $\text{pH} 5.0$. The values of k_{obs} are shown in Table 3 and the plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{NO}_3^-]$ gave a straight line (Fig. 3). It has been assumed that nitrate ion attacks the coordinated water molecule which facilitates the metal-water bond fission and catalyses the entry of incoming ligand.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF NO_3^- CONCENTRATION OF k_{obs} VALUES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN 80% (w/w) ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

$[\text{Complex-I}] = 0.0025 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ $[\text{valH}] = 0.03 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 5.0$

$[\text{NO}_3^-]$ mol dm^{-3}	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$		
	40°	45°	50°
0.02	2.01	2.61	3.55
0.03	2.15	2.70	3.65
0.04	2.20	2.80	3.80
0.05	2.38	2.95	3.85
0.06	2.45	3.04	3.95

Effect of dielectric constant on rate: Anations of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6(\text{OH})^{2+}$ by L-histidine and iminodiacetic

acid were reported^{6,7} in different ethanol-water media. Hence different organic solvents, viz. methanol, ethanol and isopropanol have been used as organic components of aquo-organic mixture to check not only the effect of the dielectric constant but also the polar nature of the organic solvent which affects the solvation of the reacting species. Effect of dielectric constant on the rate of ion-dipole typed reaction^{1,4} can be represented in a simplified way as

$$\frac{d \log k_a}{d(1/D)} = -\frac{Z^2 e^2}{kTr_0^2} \mu_{\text{valH}} \cos \theta \quad (5)$$

where, Z is the net charge on ion-pair species, r_0 the critical ion-dipole distance which is more or less the same in ground state or activated state, k the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature and D the changing dielectric constant. Now μ_{valH} is the dipole moment of the amino acid valine and θ is the angle which the negative end of the dipole makes with the line joining the center of the dipole to the complex ion. In case of associative interchange process θ will be greater than 90° because complete detachment of water molecule does not occur in the activated state, which increases the steric effect that pushes the negative end of the dipole far from its equilibrium position and hence plots of $\log k_a$ vs $1/D$ should give a straight line with a positive slope. The reverse is true for dissociative process. In practice we got a good straight line by plotting $\log k_a$ vs $1/D$ (Fig. 4)

Fig. 4. Plots of $\log k_a$ vs $1/D$ and plots of $\log K_E$ vs $1/D$ at $\text{pH} = 5.0$.

with a small positive slope expected for an associative interchange process. Increase in K_E values with the decrease of dielectric constant of the medium supports the fact that the outer sphere association is favoured in a medium of low dielectric constant. Another solvent parameter is Y (Grunwald-Winstein coefficient) which is a measure of ionising power of solvent based on the dissociative nature of solvolysis of *t*-butyl chloride¹⁵. For a dissociative process the increase in Y values increases the reaction rate which can be represented as

$$\log k = \log k_0 + mY \quad (6)$$

In our study no such linear relationship between k_a and Y of aquo-organic solvent was obtained which ruled out the possibility of dissociative process.

Effect of temperature on rate: The reaction was studied at three different temperatures in media of three different dielectric constant. Activation parameters calculated by using Eyring equation are shown in Table 4 and compared with the

TABLE 4—VALUES OF $\Delta H^\ddagger$ AND $\Delta S^\ddagger$ IN DIFFERENT AQUO-ORGANIC MIXTURES

Cr(H ₂ O) ₅ (OH) ²⁺ - DL-valine substitution in 80% (w/w)	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Isopropanol - Water	57.10	-121.66
Ethanol - Water	61.65	-109.24
Methanol - Water	68.69	-88.55

data shown for isotopic water exchange¹⁶ process and other anation reactions of the same complex. Lower values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ indicate the formation of a weak metal-ligand bond with the incoming ligand in the activated state. Change in solvent nature (organic solvent) of aquo-organic mixture changes the $\Delta S^\ddagger$ values. Negative values of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ indicate the formation of more ordered intermediate due to association which is favoured in lower dielectric medium (Table 4). As the composition of aquo-organic mixtures were kept fixed (30% w/w) in the three cases, the increase in $\Delta H^\ddagger$ value with the increase in dielectric constant of the medium is due to hindrance of interaction between complex ion and zwitterionic ligand valine at higher dielectric constant. Plots of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $T\Delta S^\ddagger$ gave a good straight line (Fig. 5), which reveals that similar transition state is formed in different aquo-organic mixture having the same composition.

Conclusion: It has been suggested that the reaction between Cr(H₂O)₅(OH)²⁺ and DL-valine involves the formation of ion-pair through the outer

Fig. 5. Plots of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $T\Delta S^\ddagger$.

sphere association and then followed by an associative interchange path in which bond formation and bond dissociation are equally important.

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